

Improved Constraints on the Heavy Gauge Bosons Decaying into a Vector Boson and a Higgs Boson at the LHC

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The full CMS and ATLAS Run 2 datasets with time-integrated luminosity of 137 and 139 fb^{-1} in the diboson channels are used to probe benchmark models with extended gauge sectors such as left-right symmetric (LR) and the sequential standard model (extended gauge model, EGM), that predict the existence of neutral Z' - and charged W' - bosons decaying to a pair of bosons ZH and WH in the semileptonic final state. These benchmark models are used to interpret the results. Exclusion limits at the 95% C.L. on the Z' and W' resonance production cross section times branching ratio to electroweak gauge boson pairs in the resonance mass range between 1.0 and 5 TeV are here converted to constraints on Z - Z' and W - W' mixing parameters and masses. We present exclusion regions on the parameter spaces of the Z' and W' and show that the obtained exclusion regions are significantly extended compared to those derived from the previous analysis performed with Tevatron data as well as with the CMS and ATLAS data collected at 7 and 8 TeV in Run 1. The reported limits are the most restrictive to date.

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1. Introduction

The search for physics beyond the Standard Model (SM) is a major focus of the physics program at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). Since its discovery, the Higgs boson has become a tool in this search. In particular, one may expect new heavy resonances to couple to Higgs bosons and weak vector bosons ($V = W$ or Z). Such resonances are expected to occur in a number of theories beyond the Standard Model. Theories that aim to solve the naturalness problem predict the existence of vector resonances as expected in composite Higgs models [1], Little Higgs models [2], or models with extra dimensions [3, 4]. The extended gauge models are among the best motivated theoretical scenarios beyond the SM

that predict the existence of new heavy neutral and charged vector bosons (Z' and W') [5, 6] with their diboson decay modes, $V' \rightarrow VV/VH$, caused by $Z - Z'$ and $W - W'$ mixing. These models are considered as benchmark scenarios for diboson resonances having spin-1 ($W' \rightarrow WZ$ or WH , $Z' \rightarrow WW$ or ZH), produced predominantly via quark-antiquark annihilation ($q\bar{q} \rightarrow W'$, $q\bar{q} \rightarrow Z'$).

Many of the searches for new physics at the LHC amount to looking for “heavy stuff”, states or resonances at masses above the scale of the electroweak vector bosons and the Higgs boson. This would be unstable and decay to jets, (add to lepton pair and neutrino pair or one can simply say fermion-antifermion pairs, $f = \nu, \ell, q$), to two $SU(2)_L$ vector bosons (VV) or to one such vector boson plus a Higgs boson (VH). If the “heavy stuff” is a gauge bosons associated with some

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additional symmetry groups, the decay could be to two fermions, to two vector bosons or to a vector boson and a Higgs boson. Events of the latter kind,

$$pp \rightarrow V'X \rightarrow VHX, \quad (1)$$

have been searched for in the resonance masses range between ~ 1.0 and 5.0 TeV in ATLAS and CMS detectors at the LHC with a total integrated luminosity of $137\text{--}139\text{ fb}^{-1}$. No significant excess is observed and 95% C.L. upper limits are placed on the production cross section times branching fraction of neutral and charged spin-1 resonances. These limits [7, 8] are converted into constraints on the parameter space (mixing vs. resonance mass) of extended gauge models.

A heavy vector boson $Z^{0'}$ associated with some new gauge group could mix with the familiar ones of $SU(2)_L$

$$Z = Z^0 \cos \phi + Z^{0'} \sin \phi, \quad (2a)$$

$$Z' = -Z^0 \sin \phi + Z^{0'} \cos \phi, \quad (2b)$$

and similar for the charged ones, W and W' . Here, the superscript “0” refers to the “pure” gauge bosons, in the absence of any mixing.

This mixing can be constrained from the non-observation of significant excess of events of the kind (1) above the estimated background. Such mixing is also constrained by the analysis of electroweak precision data and by analysis of data on the processes

$$pp \rightarrow Z'X \rightarrow WWX, \text{ and } pp \rightarrow W'X \rightarrow WZX, \quad (3)$$

where Z' and W' decaying to pairs of electroweak vector bosons (jointly referred to as V in the following with $V = W, Z$), and SM Higgs (H) bosons.

In the simplest models under study such as the Sequential Standard Model (SSM) [9] new neutral Z'_{SSM} and charged W'_{SSM} bosons have couplings to fermions that are identical to those of the SM Z and W bosons, but for which the trilinear couplings $Z'WW$ and $W'WZ$ are absent,

$g_{Z'WW} = 0$ and $g_{W'WZ} = 0$. This suppression may arise naturally in an EGM: if the new gauge bosons and the SM ones belong to different gauge groups, a vertex such as $Z'WW$ ($W'WZ$) is forbidden. They can only be induced after symmetry breaking due to mixing of the gauge eigenstates.

The properties of possible Z' and W' bosons are also constrained by measurements of electroweak (EW) processes at low energies, i.e., at energies much below their masses. Such bounds on the Z - Z' (W - W') mixing are mostly due to the constraints on deviation in Z (W) properties from the SM predictions. In particular, limits from direct hadron production with subsequent diboson decay at the Tevatron [10] and from virtual effects at LEP, through interference or mixing with the Z boson, imply that any new Z' boson is rather heavy and mixes very little with the Z boson. The measurements show that the mixing angles, referred to as $\xi_{Z-Z'}$ and $\xi_{W-W'}$, between the gauge eigenstates must be smaller than about 10^{-3} and 10^{-2} , respectively [5].

Previous analyses of the Z - Z' and W - W' mixing [11, 12] were carried out using the diboson production data set corresponding to the time-integrated luminosity of $\sim 36\text{ fb}^{-1}$ collected in 2015 and 2016 with the ATLAS and CMS collaborations at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV where, in the former case, electroweak Z and W gauge bosons decay into the semileptonic channel or into the dijet final state. Further updated results were obtained using the diboson and dilepton Run 2 production data set corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 139 fb^{-1} [13, 14] recorded by the ATLAS detector. In the analysis presented here, we utilize the full Run 2 CMS and ATLAS data set on diboson resonance production published recently in Refs. [7, 8] for the VV and VH channels corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 137 fb^{-1} .

Another class of models considered here are those inspired by Grand Unified Theories (GUT), which are motivated by gauge unification or a restoration of the left-right symmetry violated by the weak interaction. Examples

considered in this paper include the Z' bosons of the E_6 -motivated [6] theories and high-mass neutral bosons of the left-right (LR) symmetric extensions of the SM, based on the $SU(2)_L \otimes SU(2)_R \otimes U(1)_{B-L}$ gauge group, where $B - L$ refers to the difference between baryon and lepton numbers.

The paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2 we present the theoretical framework, then, in Sects. 3 and 4 we review the production and decay of W' and Z' , respectively. Finally, Sect. 5 contains concluding remarks.

2. $V-V'$ mixing

As mentioned above, in the SSM, the coupling constants of the W' and Z' bosons with SM fermions are identical to the corresponding SM couplings, while the W' and Z' couplings to, respectively, WZ and WW vanish, $g_{W'WZ} = g_{Z'WW} = 0$. Such a suppression may arise in an EGM in a natural manner: if the new gauge bosons and those of the SM belong to different gauge groups, vertices such as $W'WZ$ and $Z'WW$ do not arise. They can only occur after symmetry breaking due to mixing of the gauge eigenstates. Triple gauge boson couplings (such as $W'WZ$ and $Z'WW$) as well as the vector-vector-scalar couplings (like $W'WH$ and $Z'ZH$) arise from the symmetry breaking and may contribute to the W' and Z' decays, respectively. The vertices are then suppressed by a factor of the order of $(M_W/M_{V'})^2$, where V' represents a W' or a Z' boson.

In an EGM [9], the trilinear gauge boson couplings are modified by mixing factors

$$\xi_{V-V'} = \mathcal{C} \times (M_W/M_{V'})^2, \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{C} is a scaling constant that sets the coupling strength. Note that the EGM can be parametrized either in terms of $(M_{V'}, \mathcal{C})$ or in terms of $(M_{V'}, \xi_{V-V'})$. Specifically, in an EGM the standard-model trilinear gauge boson coupling strength g_{WWZ} ($= e \cot \theta_W$), is replaced by $g_{W'WZ} = \xi_{W-W'} \cdot g_{WWZ}$ in the WZ channel

and $g_{Z'WW} = \xi_{Z-Z'} \cdot g_{WWZ}$ in the WW channel. We follow a parametrization of the trilinear gauge boson couplings $W'WZ$ and $Z'WW$ for analyzing and interpreting the CDF data on $p\bar{p} \rightarrow W'X \rightarrow WZX$ and $p\bar{p} \rightarrow Z'X \rightarrow W^+W^-X$ which are expressed in terms of two free parameters, $\xi_{W-W'}$ ($\xi_{Z-Z'}$) and $M_{W'}$ ($M_{Z'}$). Such W' and Z' , described in terms of the two parameters (mass and mixing), are here referred to as EGM bosons. The parametrization is presented in [10]. Then, we will set two-dimensional limits, by using the CMS and ATLAS resonant diboson production data [7, 8] collected in the full Run 2 data set with time-integrated luminosity of 137 fb^{-1} and 139 fb^{-1} , respectively. The presented analysis in the EGM with two free parameters is more general than the previous ones where the only parameter is the V' mass. As for the SSM, one has $V'_{\text{SSM}} \equiv V'_{\text{EGM}}$ when $\xi_{V-V'} = 0$.

Note that the parametrization of boson mixing introduced by Altarelli *et al.* [9], though being simplified, has a well-motivated theoretical basis. To be specific, we briefly consider $Z^0-Z'^0$ mixing within the framework of models with extended gauge sector. The mass eigenstates Z and Z' are admixtures of the weak eigenstates Z^0 of $SU(2) \times U(1)$ and Z'^0 of the extra $U(1)'$, respectively:

$$Z = Z^0 \cos \phi + Z'^0 \sin \phi, \quad (5a)$$

$$Z' = -Z^0 \sin \phi + Z'^0 \cos \phi. \quad (5b)$$

In each case there is a relation between the $Z^0-Z'^0$ mixing angle ϕ and the masses M_Z and $M_{Z'}$ [6]:

$$\tan^2 \phi = \frac{M_{Z^0}^2 - M_Z^2}{M_{Z'}^2 - M_{Z^0}^2} \simeq \frac{2 M_{Z^0} \Delta M_{Z^0 Z}}{M_{Z'}^2}, \quad (6)$$

where the downward shift $\Delta M_{Z^0 Z} = M_{Z^0} - M_Z > 0$, and M_{Z^0} is the mass of the Z boson in the absence of mixing, i.e., for $\phi = 0$, given by

$$M_{Z^0} = \frac{M_W}{\sqrt{\rho_0} \cos \theta_W}, \quad (7)$$

in terms of the charged (M_W) gauge boson mass and the ρ_0 parameter. The mixing angle

ϕ will play an important role in our analysis. Such mixing effects reflect the underlying gauge symmetry and/or the structure of the Higgs sector of the model as the ρ_0 parameter depends on the ratios of the Higgs vacuum expectation values and on the total and third components of weak isospin of the Higgs fields. For each type of $Z^{0'}$ boson, defined by its gauge couplings, there are three classes of models, which differ in the assumptions concerning the quantum numbers of the Higgs fields which generate the Z -boson mass matrix [6].

- (i) The least constrained (ρ_0 free) model makes no assumption concerning the Higgs sector. It allows arbitrary $SU(2)$ representations for the Higgs fields, and is the analogue of allowing $\rho_0 \neq 1$ in the $SU(2) \times U(1)$ model. In this case M_Z , $M_{Z'}$ and ϕ are all free parameters.
- (ii) If one assumes that all $SU(2)$ breaking is due to Higgs doublets and singlets ($\rho_0 = 1$ model), there are only two free parameters, which we identify as ϕ and $M_{Z'}$. We will adopt this parametrization throughout the paper.
- (iii) Finally, in specific models one specifies not only the $SU(2)$ assignments but the $U(1)'$ assignments of the Higgs fields. Since the same Higgs multiplets generate both M_Z and ϕ , one has an additional constraint. To a good approximation, for $M_Z \ll M_{Z'}$, in specific “minimal-Higgs models”, one has an additional constraint

$$\phi \simeq -s_W^2 \frac{\sum_i \langle \Phi_i \rangle^2 I_{3L}^i Q_i'}{\sum_i \langle \Phi_i \rangle^2 (I_{3L}^i)^2} = P \frac{M_Z^2}{M_{Z'}^2}, \quad (8)$$

where s_W is the sine of the electroweak angle. In these models ϕ and $M_{Z'}$ are not independent and there is only one (e.g., $M_{Z'}$) free parameter. This parametrization is of the form presented in Eq. (4). Furthermore, $\langle \Phi_i \rangle$ are the Higgs (doublet) vacuum expectation values

spontaneously breaking the symmetry, and Q_i' are their charges with respect to the additional $U(1)'$. In these models the same Higgs multiplets are responsible for both generation of the mass M_Z and for the strength of the Z^0 - $Z^{0'}$ mixing. Thus P is a model-dependent constant.

This Z^0 - $Z^{0'}$ mixing induces a change in the couplings of the two bosons to fermions. From Eq. (5), one obtains the vector and axial-vector couplings of the Z and Z' bosons to fermions:

$$v_f = v_f^0 \cos \phi + v_f^{0'} \sin \phi, a_f = a_f^0 \cos \phi + a_f^{0'} \sin \phi, \quad (9a)$$

$$v_f' = v_f^0 \cos \phi - v_f^{0'} \sin \phi, a_f' = a_f^0 \cos \phi - a_f^{0'} \sin \phi, \quad (9b)$$

with unprimed and primed couplings referring to Z^0 and $Z^{0'}$, respectively, and found, e.g. in [6].

An important property of the models under consideration is that the gauge eigenstate $Z^{0'}$ does not couple to the W^+W^- pair since it is neutral under $SU(2)$. Therefore the W -pair production is sensitive to a Z' only to the extent that there is a non-zero Z^0 - $Z^{0'}$ mixing. From Eq. (5), one obtains:

$$g_{WWZ} = \cos \phi g_{WWZ^0}, \quad (10a)$$

$$g_{WWZ'} = -\sin \phi g_{WWZ^0}, \quad (10b)$$

where $g_{WWZ^0} = e \cot \theta_W$. Also, $g_{WW\gamma} = e$.

In many extended gauge models, while the couplings to fermions are not much different from those of the SM, the $Z'WW$ coupling is substantially suppressed with respect to that of the SM. In fact, in the extended gauge models the SM trilinear gauge boson coupling strength, g_{WWZ^0} , is replaced by $g_{WWZ^0} \rightarrow \xi_{Z-Z'} \cdot g_{WWZ^0}$, where $\xi_{Z-Z'} \equiv |\sin \phi|$ (see Eq. (10b)) is the mixing factor. We will set cross section limits on such Z' as functions of the mass $M_{Z'}$ and $\xi_{Z-Z'}$.

In addition, we study W - W' mixing in the process $pp \rightarrow V'X \rightarrow VHX$ within the framework of the EGM model. Mass mixing may be induced between the electrically charged gauge bosons at the tree level. The physical (mass)

eigenstates of W and W' are admixtures of the weak eigenstates denoted as \hat{W} and \hat{W}' , respectively, and obtained by a rotation of those fields:

$$W^\pm = \hat{W}^\pm \cos \theta_{WW'} + \hat{W}'^\pm \sin \theta_{WW'}, \quad (11a)$$

$$W'^\pm = -\hat{W}^\pm \sin \theta_{WW'} + \hat{W}'^\pm \cos \theta_{WW'}, \quad (11b)$$

in analogy with Eq. (5). Upon diagonalization of their mass matrix, the couplings of the observed W boson are shifted from the SM values. The mixing parameter $\xi_{W-W'}$ between gauge eigenstates can be defined as $\xi_{W-W'} \equiv |\sin \theta_{WW'}|$.

3. Hadron production and decay of W' boson

In this section, we consider the simplest EGM model which predicts charged heavy gauge bosons. At the lowest order in the EGM, W' production and decay into WZ and WH in proton-proton collisions occur through quark-antiquark annihilation in the s -channel. Adopting the Narrow-Width Approximation (NWA), one can factorize the process (1) into the W' production and the W' decay,

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow W'X \rightarrow WZ X) = \sigma(pp \rightarrow W' X) \times \text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WZ), \quad (12a)$$

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow W'X \rightarrow WH X) = \sigma(pp \rightarrow W' X) \times \text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH). \quad (12b)$$

Here, $\sigma(pp \rightarrow W'X)$ is the total (theoretical) W' production cross section, $\text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WZ) = \Gamma_{W'}^{WZ}/\Gamma_{W'}$ and similarly $\text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH) = \Gamma_{W'}^{WH}/\Gamma_{W'}$ with $\Gamma_{W'}$ the total width of the W' .

In the EGM the W' bosons can decay into pairs of SM fermions (charged leptons,

neutrinos and quarks), gauge bosons WZ and WH . Specifically, in the calculation of the total width $\Gamma_{W'}$ we consider the following channels: $W' \rightarrow f\bar{f}'$, WZ , and WH , where f is a SM fermion ($f = \ell, \nu, q$). Note, that here the ℓ includes τ leptons as well. Only the familiar left-handed neutrinos are considered, possible right-handed exotic neutrinos are assumed to be kinematically unavailable as final states. Also, we shall ignore the couplings to other beyond-SM particles such as SUSY partners and exotic fermions. As a result, the total decay width of the W' boson is taken to be

$$\Gamma_{W'} = \sum_f \Gamma_{W'}^{f\bar{f}'} + \Gamma_{W'}^{WZ} + \Gamma_{W'}^{WH}. \quad (13)$$

The presence of the last two decay channels, which are often neglected at low and moderate values of $M_{W'}$, is due to W - W' mixing which is constrained to be tiny. In particular, for the range of $M_{W'}$ values below ~ 2 TeV, the dependence of $\Gamma_{W'}$ on the values of $\xi_{W-W'}$ (within its allowed range) induced by $\Gamma_{W'}^{WZ}$ and $\Gamma_{W'}^{WH}$ is unimportant because $\sum_f \Gamma_{W'}^{f\bar{f}'}$ highly dominates over the diboson partial widths as illustrated in fig. 1 for a representative value of the mixing parameter. Therefore, in this mass range, one can approximate the total width as $\Gamma_{W'} \approx \sum_f \Gamma_{W'}^{f\bar{f}'} = 3.5\% \times M_{W'}$ [11], where the sum runs over SM fermions only. For heavier W' bosons, the diboson decay channels, WZ and WH , start to play an important role, and we are no longer able to ignore them [11–14]. To be specific, we assume that both partial widths are comparable, $\Gamma_{W'}^{WH} \simeq \Gamma_{W'}^{WZ}$ for heavy $M_{W'}$, as required by the Equivalence theorem.

The partial width of the $W' \rightarrow WZ$ decay channel in the EGM can be written as [9, 11, 13]:

$$\Gamma_{W'}^{WZ} = \frac{\alpha_{\text{em}}}{48} \cot^2 \theta_W M_{W'} \frac{M_{W'}^4}{M_W^2 M_Z^2} \left[\left(1 - \frac{M_Z^2 - M_W^2}{M_{W'}^2} \right)^2 - 4 \frac{M_W^2}{M_{W'}^2} \right]^{3/2} \times \left[1 + 10 \left(\frac{M_W^2 + M_Z^2}{M_{W'}^2} \right) + \frac{M_W^4 + M_Z^4 + 10 M_W^2 M_Z^2}{M_{W'}^4} \right] \cdot \xi_{W-W'}^2. \quad (14)$$

For a fixed mixing factor $\xi_{W-W'}$ and at large $M_{W'}$, the total width increases rapidly with the W' mass because of the quintic dependence of the WZ mode on the W' mass $\Gamma_{W'}^{WZ} \propto M_{W'} [M_{W'}^4 / (M_W^2 M_Z^2)]$, corresponding to the production of longitudinally polarized W and Z in the channel $W' \rightarrow W_L Z_L$ [9]. In this case, the WZ mode (as well as WH) becomes dominant and $\text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WZ) \rightarrow 0.5$, while the fermionic decay channels, $\sum_f \Gamma_{W'}^{ff'} \propto M_{W'}$, are increasingly suppressed, as illustrated in fig. 1.

FIG. 1. Branching ratios $\text{BR}(W' \rightarrow \sum f \bar{f}')$ (solid), $\text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH)$ (dash-dotted), and $\text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH + WZ)$ (dashed) vs $M_{W'}$ in the EGM where the W - W' mixing factor is taken to be $\xi_{W-W'} = 3 \cdot 10^{-3}$. It is assumed that $\text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WZ) = \text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH)$.

The data we consider were collected with the CMS and ATLAS detectors during the 2015–2018 running period of the LHC, referred to as Run 2 and correspond to a time-integrated luminosity of 137 fb^{-1} and 139 fb^{-1} , respectively. The

CMS and ATLAS experiments have presented the recent search for diboson resonances based on the full Run 2 datasets in the semileptonic final states [7, 8] and set limits on the W' production cross sections times branching fraction in the process $pp \rightarrow W'X \rightarrow WHX$ for $M_{W'}$ in the 1.0 TeV – 4.5–5 TeV range. In fig. 2, we show the observed 95% C.L. upper limits on the production cross section times the branching fraction, $\sigma_{95\%} \times \text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH)$, as functions of the W' mass. The area below the long-dashed curve labelled “NWA” corresponds to the region where the W' resonance width is predicted to be less than 5% of its mass, corresponding to the best detector resolution of the searches, where the narrow-width assumption is satisfied. We also show a curve labelled “Unitarity limit” that corresponds to the unitarity bound (see, e.g. [11, 13]). The intersection points of the measured upper limits on the production cross section with these theoretical cross sections for various values of $\xi_{W-W'}$ give the corresponding upper bounds on $\xi_{W-W'}$, displayed in fig. 3. Our results extend the sensitivity much beyond the corresponding CDF Tevatron results as well as the ATLAS and CMS sensitivity attained at 7 and 8 TeV. Also, for the first time, we set W' limits as functions of the mass $M_{W'}$ and mixing factor $\xi_{W-W'}$ from the study of the diboson production and subsequent decay into semileptonic final states at the LHC at 13 TeV with the full CMS Run 2 datasets. The exclusion region obtained in this way on the parameter space of the W' naturally supersedes the corresponding exclusion area obtained for time-integrated luminosity of 36.1 fb^{-1} at CMS in the semileptonic channel as reported in [12, 14–17]. The limits on the

FIG. 2. 95% C.L. upper limits on $\sigma_{95\%} \times \text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH)$, showing CMS and ATLAS data on the semileptonic final states for 137 fb^{-1} and 139 fb^{-1} . The theoretical production cross sections $\sigma(pp \rightarrow W'X) \times \text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH)$ for the EGM.

W' parameters presented in this section obtained from the diboson WH production in semileptonic final states, corresponding to a time-integrated luminosity of 137 fb^{-1} (CMS) and 139 fb^{-1} (ATLAS).

4. Hadron production and decay of Z' boson

We shall next consider Z' boson production in pp collision and its subsequent decay into diboson channels, $Z' \rightarrow W^+W^-$ and $Z' \rightarrow ZH$. Specifically, we concentrate on the models with extended gauge sector predicting the existence of Z' bosons, such as E_6 , left-right symmetric LR and the EGM. The processes under study are:

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'X \rightarrow W^+W^-X) = \sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'X) \times \text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow W^+W^-), \quad (15a)$$

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'X \rightarrow ZHX) = \sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'X) \times \text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow ZH). \quad (15b)$$

Here, $\sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'X)$ is the total (theoretical) Z' production cross section, $\text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow W^+W^-) = \Gamma_{Z'W^+W^-} / \Gamma_{Z'}$ and $\text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow ZH) = \Gamma_{Z'ZH} / \Gamma_{Z'}$ with

FIG. 3. 95% C.L. exclusion regions in the two-dimensional $(M_{W'}, \xi_{W-W'})$ plane obtained from the precision electroweak data (horizontal dashed straight line labeled “EW”), direct search constraints from the Tevatron in $p\bar{p} \rightarrow WZX$ (dark shaded area) as well as from the LHC searches for $pp \rightarrow WZX$ at 7 TeV and 8 TeV (Run 1) (gray area) and at 13 TeV from $W' \rightarrow WH$ production in semileptonic final states using the full Run 2 ATLAS and CMS datasets. The region above each curve for the WZH channel is excluded.

$\Gamma_{Z'}$ the total width of the Z' . Among the Z' models, we start out with a discussion of the EGM. In the computation of the total width $\Gamma_{Z'}$ we take into account the following channels: $Z' \rightarrow f\bar{f}$, W^+W^- , and ZH [13, 14], where H is the SM Higgs boson and f refers to the SM fermions ($f = l, \nu, q$). Throughout the paper we shall ignore the couplings of the Z' to any beyond-

FIG. 4. 95% C.L. upper limits on $\sigma_{95\%} \times \text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow ZH)$, showing CMS and ATLAS data on the semileptonic final states for 137 fb^{-1} and 139 fb^{-1} , respectively. .

SM particles such as right-handed neutrinos, as well as to SUSY partners and any other exotic fermions. Any additional states may increase the width of the Z' . The total width $\Gamma_{Z'}$ of the Z' boson can then be written as follows:

$$\Gamma_{Z'} = \sum_f \Gamma_{Z'}^{ff} + \Gamma_{Z'}^{WW} + \Gamma_{Z'}^{ZH}. \quad (16)$$

The two last terms are due to Z - Z' mixing. For the range of $M_{Z'}$ values below ~ 3 TeV, the dependence of $\Gamma_{Z'}$ on the values of $\xi_{Z-Z'}$ (within its allowed range) is unimportant. Therefore, in this mass range, one can approximate the total width as $\Gamma_{Z'} \approx \sum_f \Gamma_{Z'}^{ff}$, where the sum runs over SM fermions only. Within the approximation above, one can quantify the ratio of $\Gamma_{Z'}/M_{Z'}$ for the benchmark EGM as 3%, whereas for the ψ , η , χ and LR models it varies from 0.5% to 2.0%. We note that the ‘‘Equivalence theorem’’ suggests a value for $\text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow ZH)$ comparable to $\text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow W^+W^-)$, up to electroweak symmetry breaking effects and phase-space factors. Throughout this paper, for definiteness, we adopt a scenario where both partial widths are comparable, $\Gamma_{Z'}^{ZH} \simeq \Gamma_{Z'}^{WW}$ for

heavy $M_{Z'}$. For all $M_{Z'}$ values of interest for our analysis the width of the Z' boson is considerably

FIG. 5. The Z'_{EGM} model: 95% C.L. exclusion regions in the two-dimensional $(M_{Z'}, \xi_{Z-Z'})$ plane obtained after incorporating indirect constraints from electroweak precision data (dashed curve labeled ‘‘EW’’), and direct search constraints from the Tevatron (dark shaded area) as well as from the LHC searches for $pp \rightarrow Z' \rightarrow ZH$ in semileptonic final states using the full Run 2 CMS and ATLAS datasets. The region above the curves for ZH channels are excluded.

smaller than the experimental mass resolution ΔM . We adopt the approximation $\Delta M/M \approx 5\%$, as reported, e.g., in for reconstructing the diboson invariant mass of the ZH systems. The partial width of the $Z' \rightarrow W^+W^-$ decay channel can be written as:

$$\Gamma_{Z'}^{WW} = \frac{\alpha}{48} \cot^2 \theta_W M_{Z'} \left(\frac{M_{Z'}}{M_W} \right)^4 \left(1 - 4 \frac{M_W^2}{M_{Z'}^2} \right)^{3/2} \left[1 + 20 \left(\frac{M_W}{M_{Z'}} \right)^2 + 12 \left(\frac{M_W}{M_{Z'}} \right)^4 \right] \xi_{Z-Z'}^2. \quad (17)$$

For a fixed mixing factor $\xi_{Z-Z'}$ and at large $M_{Z'}$ where $\Gamma_{Z'}^{WW}$ dominates over $\sum_f \Gamma_{Z'}^{ff}$ the total width increases rapidly with the mass $M_{Z'}$ because of the quintic dependence of the W^+W^- mode on the Z' mass. In this case, the W^+W^- mode (together with $Z' \rightarrow ZH$) becomes dominant and $\text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow W^+W^-) \rightarrow 0.5$ (this value arises from the assumption $\Gamma_{Z'}^{ZH} = \Gamma_{Z'}^{WW}$), while the fermionic decay channels ($\Gamma_{Z'}^{ff} \propto M_{Z'}$) are increasingly suppressed.

In fig. 4, we consider the full CMS and ATLAS Run2 datasets of time integrated luminosity of 137 fb^{-1} and 139 fb^{-1} and show the observed 95% C.L. upper limits on the production cross section times the branching fraction, $\sigma_{95\%} \times \text{BR}(Z'_{\text{EGM}} \rightarrow ZH)$, as functions of the Z' mass, obtained from the semileptonic final state.

FIG. 6. 95% C.L. upper limits on $\sigma_{95\%} \times \text{BR}(Z'_{LR} \rightarrow ZH)$, showing CMS and ATLAS data on the semileptonic final states for 137 fb^{-1} and 139 fb^{-1} , respectively.

Different bounds on the Z' parameter space are collected in fig. 5, for the Z'_{EGM} model,

FIG. 7. 95% C.L. upper limits on $\sigma_{95\%} \times \text{BR}(Z'_{LR} \rightarrow ZH)$, showing CMS and ATLAS data on the semileptonic final states for 137 fb^{-1} and 139 fb^{-1} , respectively. The theoretical production cross sections $\sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'X) \times \text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow WW)$ for the EGM for mixing factor $\xi_{Z-Z'}$.

showing that at high masses, the limits on $\xi_{Z-Z'}$ obtained from the full Run 2 datasets collected at $\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$ and recorded by the CMS and ATLAS detectors are substantially stronger than that derived from the global analysis of the precision electroweak data (EW), as well as

the limits obtained from diboson data at the Tevatron.

The analysis of Z - Z' mixing, performed here for the EGM, can also be carried out for the other benchmark models. The results of the numerical analysis for these models are shown in fig. 6-7. Limits on a Z'_{LR} are calculated as the intersection between the observed limits, $\sigma_{95\%} \times \text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow ZH)$, with the model prediction, $\sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'_{LR}X) \times \text{BR}(Z'_{LR} \rightarrow ZH)$, respectively.

5. Conclusion

Exploration of the diboson WH and ZH production at the LHC with the 13 TeV datasets allows to place stringent constraints on the W - W' and Z - Z' mixing parameters in the resonance mass range between ~ 1.0 TeV and 5 TeV. We derived such limits by using the full CMS and ATLAS Run 2 datasets recorded at the CERN LHC, with integrated luminosity of 137 fb^{-1} (CMS) and 139 fb^{-1} (ATLAS), respectively. By comparing the experimental limits to the theoretical predictions for the total cross section

of the W' and Z' resonant production and its subsequent decay into WH and ZH pairs, $\sigma(pp \rightarrow W'X) \times \text{BR}(W' \rightarrow WH)$ and $\sigma(pp \rightarrow Z'X) \times \text{BR}(Z' \rightarrow ZH)$, we show that the derived limits on the mixing parameters, $\xi_{W-W'}$ and $\xi_{Z-Z'}$, for the benchmark models, are substantially improved (of the order of a few $\times 10^{-4}$) with respect to those obtained from the global analysis of low-energy electroweak data (EW), as well as from the diboson production study performed at the Tevatron and those based on the CMS Run 1 and on the CMS Run 2 at time-integrated luminosity of $\sim 36 \text{ fb}^{-1}$. Further constraining of this mixing can be achieved from the analysis of future CMS and ATLAS data to be collected in Run 3 as well as at the next options of hadron colliders such as HL-LHC and HE-LHC as demonstrated in [13] for the ATLAS experiment.

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